

COOPERATION OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AUTHORITIES IN THE SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS OF CAUSES OF COMMITMENT OF CRIMES AND ISSUES OF ITS IMPROVEMENT

Muhsinbek Kholmiraev

Law enforcement agencies independent student of the academy

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Abstract. *In this article, the general situation of mutual cooperation of law enforcement agencies in the systematic analysis of the causes of crimes today, the shortcomings in the field, the comparative analysis of foreign and national experience in increasing the efficiency of cooperation, as well as the reasonable hypotheses about how inter-agency cooperation in this field will be in the future are reflected in this article.*

Keywords: *forensics, forensics, body cameras, facial recognition, number plate recognition, kernel analytics, neural networks, heuristic engines, recursive processors, Bayesian networks, data mining, cryptographic algorithms, document processors, computational linguistics, voiceprint identification, natural language processing, gait analysis, biometric recognition.*

Over the past period, significant work has been carried out in our country on the basis of close cooperation between state bodies and institutions of civil society, to maintain public order, to introduce a qualitatively new system of crime prevention and fight against crime, to ensure reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of citizens.

However, these reforms are losing their influence and importance.

Now, in the fight against crime, exposing crimes, investigating them, and carrying out propaganda activities about them after they have been committed have become ineffective.

These methods are closely related to the obsolescence of the population, the large-scale expansion of the sphere of social relations, and the increase in the number of crimes.

Now, time itself shows that early detection and prevention of crimes through scientific analysis of crime mechanisms, causes of their origin, conditions for crime commission and modern gadgets and software is becoming a priority in fighting crime.

In this activity, it is important to maintain criminal-legal statistics and introduce an effective system of crime analysis, which allows to determine the criminogenic situation in the country with great accuracy, to identify the current problems and shortcomings of the current mechanisms for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, as well as to develop comprehensively thought-out prospects for their improvement takes place.

At the same time, the analysis of the work carried out in the field of crime statistics shows that the implementation of systematic analysis and quality control, the implementation of prosecutor's control in criminal forecasting, and the introduction of modern information technologies that ensure accurate, reliable and more competent processing of data, data collection and processing there is a need to improve the current working mechanisms.

As we all know, on the basis of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 31.10.2018 No. PF-5566 on measures to fundamentally improve the system of criminal and

legal statistics and increase the efficiency of systematic analysis of crimes, systematic analysis and study of the causes of crimes in the structure of the Academy of Law Enforcement Bodies center was established.

The tasks of the center include studying and diagnosing the causes and conditions of crimes, prevention of crimes, including analysis of the state of prevention of certain types of crimes, criminological forecasting of changes in the crime situation, as well as methodological and consultative provision of crime prevention activities, prevention of crimes and development of scientifically based suggestions and recommendations for elimination, as well as monitoring their implementation, and carrying out scientific and practical research on types of crimes, the identity of criminals and victims, have been defined.

In order to achieve the goals and objectives of this Decree, on February 15, 2019, the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the Ministry of Justice jointly conducted a systematic analysis and study of the causes of crimes to increase the efficiency of inter-agency cooperation joint decision on measures was developed.

In the framework of this joint decision, an expert-analytical group was formed under the leadership of district prosecutors in each district (city) of the Republic, which included the relevant prosecutor's office, internal affairs, alliya, state tax, customs, health, employment and labor relations, education management bodies, representatives of women's committees, self-management bodies, "Nuroni" fund, "Mahalla" fund, Youth Union were included.

Also, it is established that responsible employees of the bodies, scientists, psychologists, jurists, economists, as well as foreign experts and other specialists can be involved in the activities of the Center and expert-analysis groups.

However, it should be noted that the center and expert analysis groups study and diagnose the causes and conditions of crimes, prevention of crimes, including analysis of the situation of prevention of certain types of crimes, criminological forecasting of changes in the crime situation, as well as methodological support of crime prevention activities. consultative should be ensured.

However, it should be noted here that there are no specific legal grounds on how the changes in crime should be carried out by the expert analysis groups, using what methods and methods.

Therefore, there is a need to adopt a normative legal document regulating the field of criminological forecasting of crime.

These cases indicate that mechanisms for working with statistical data and other types of data have not been formed.

The lack of a specific algorithm in the analysis and prediction of the causes of crime is the basis for the analysis of data based on the "fantasy" of a certain subject.

In addition, there are no criteria for the reliability, validity and standard of the information used in criminal forecasting.

Such situations, in turn, have a negative impact on the formation of different views in all districts (cities) and, as a result, on the emergence of a single alternative practice.

Although expert-analytical groups established in districts (cities) are supposed to develop work plans for every six months, in practice, due to insufficient assessment of the effectiveness of planning assumptions and measures, the developed work plans are mostly ineffective.

A 6-month analysis is made by expert analysis teams based on the categories of crimes committed in the current year.

For example, in 2021, 14 types of crimes were committed in Khojaly district, and in 2022, 24 types of crimes were committed. The expert analysis groups developed a work plan and a plan of measures based on it to prevent the commission of 14 types of crimes.

The reason for the occurrence of such cases is the fact that the theoretical foundations of crime forecasting procedures, periods, and methods have not been created.

In addition, the methods and tools carried out by the employees are not continued by the employees who replaced them, and as a result, the initially determined measures are not completed, and it is not possible to evaluate their effectiveness.

For this reason, there is a need to improve the activities of expert analysis groups and digitize this field.

It should be noted that the conclusions and recommendations given by the Center and expert-analysis groups must be considered by the organizations responsible for the prevention of crimes, and the result should be known.

However, the recommendations and conclusions are mostly of one-time value and have not become an integral part of the general practice.

As a result of the centralized analysis of the conclusions and recommendations and the reliance on statistical data alone, measures remain insufficiently developed.

As we all know, the regions differ from each other in terms of their location, geographical features, tibia, and demographic aspects.

Therefore, in our opinion, we believe that it is necessary to establish regional crime laboratories consisting of professional staff in districts (cities).

By applying various methods of crime prediction and prevention, it is possible to change the scenario of law enforcement agencies and thereby achieve systematic continuous assurance of effectiveness.

In the near future, by combining ML and computer vision, security equipment such as surveillance cameras and detection circles, a machine can understand what a crime actually is by learning the pattern of past crimes and accurately predict future crimes without human intervention.

To implement this situation, it is possible to classify crimes and develop their algorithm in a certain software.

Currently, similar software has been developed in a number of countries, for example, we can cite the "Predpol" program, which is showing its results in the USA. Based on the information given about the "hot areas" and "times" where crime can be committed by using this program, it is felt that the indicators of crime will decrease by 20 percent.

In the fight against crime, crime can be prevented by alerting the law enforcement agencies and exercising more control in the forecast area due to the wide use of ICT capabilities.

Crime forecasting should be analyzed on the basis of various modern gadgets.

Currently, in advanced foreign countries, body cameras, facial recognition, number plate recognition, kernel analytics, neural networks, heuristic engines, recursive processors, Bayesian networks, data mining, cryptographic algorithms, document processors, computational linguistics, voice print recognition, natural language processing, gait analysis, biometric recognition, template analysis, interpretation of threats, detection, classification of threats is widely used ICT capabilities.

As a result of our proposals, crime forecasting is fully computer-analyzed, ready-to-use results, and works without human interaction.

The use of modern tools and methods of crime prediction increases the level of safety in society by reducing the incidence of crime.

Investing in predictive measures increases the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies by helping them manage their available resources and keep a constant watch on high-crime areas.

In addition, effective tools increase the accuracy and quality of decisions made by heads of bodies that ensure prevention and community peace. The concept of predictive policing is based on the fact that human behavior follows certain patterns that can be learned through big data analysis. This increases the relevance of the concept of big data in the field of law enforcement.

Gadgets built on the basis of modern technologies and artificial intelligence contribute to the widespread use of big data in predictive policing, enabling the analysis of large amounts of data in a short period of time.

Software and computer programs developed by various technology companies have enabled law enforcement agencies to use systematic and algorithm-based data to predict crimes, increasing efficiency.

As a result of the above legal-social and legal-economic analysis, we can conclude the following.

First, it is necessary to introduce software based on artificial intelligence in order to ensure effective cooperation of law enforcement agencies in the systematic analysis of the causes of crimes.

Secondly, there is a need to improve the activities of expert-analytical groups operating in the form of community organized in districts (cities). For this reason, it is necessary to establish crime criminological and criminological laboratories at regional prosecutor's offices consisting of professional staff.

Thirdly, it is necessary to develop sectoral orders and guidelines for the activity of criminological forecasting of crime.

Fourthly, the method of evaluating the data obtained as a result of crime forecasting is to determine the methods.

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